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Blockchain architectures for enhancing EV infrastructure security: A unified framework for addressing sophisticated cyber-attacks

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ABSTRACT

Over the last years the Electric Vehicles (EVs) are gradually adopted by users, as they have environmental, technological and financial benefits with respect to combustion engine vehicles. However, the abundance of connectivity interfaces constitutes them prone to cyber-attack scenarios targeting the entire infrastructure and especially the EVs, the EV Charging Stations as well as the Charging Station Management System that is used for their management, control and configuration. The cyber-attacks have increasing impact and risk as they may further propagate to the electrical grid, causing cascading effects as utility service disruptions or blackouts. The impact analysis though requires a threat taxonomy related to their Tactics, Techniques and Procedures (TTPs) and an associated risk model, allowing to select the most prominent threats in the EV infrastructure. Additionally, such threats are currently detected and mitigated by anomaly detection systems also using Machine Learning systems, which nevertheless do not consider the distributed nature of EV infrastructures.

The high level overarching objective of this article is three-fold: 1) to provide an initial security posture assessment of EV ecosystems as a reference point against which a detailed risk model is presented; 2) to identify the best practices and integration patterns in the adoption of blockchain technology to EV ecosystems for addressing EV-oriented attacks; and 3) to propose a blockchain-oriented architecture for the protection of the distributed EV ecosystems against cyber-attacks, which is also validated in a proof-of-concept infrastructure. The proposed approach presents a comprehensive Zero-Trust architecture for securing and unifying EV services across retail EV charging, energy trading, and energy management. The analysis illustrates data models, settlement and control flows, but also the security properties established, via a unified blockchain framework, assuming realistic adversarial capabilities.

1. Introduction

Cyber-attacks in EVs have risen substantially over the past few years. The EVs and EV Charging Stations (EVCS) are used as a threat vector for exposing sensitive information about the drivers (e.g., location), such as the vulnerability that was discovered recently in Volkswagen EVs [1], as well as earlier attacks with financial impact for the customers of a large EV infrastructure operator [2].

These attacks' increasing rate occurs due to the growing number of connectivity interfaces and threat vectors in the EV-oriented infrastructure [3]. When such threat vectors are also linked with vulnerabilities on the individual systems of the infrastructure (i.e., EVCS or CSMS), the risk of adversaries gaining unauthorized access increases. On top of such risk, given that systems such as the EVCS or Charging Station Management System (CSMS) usually originate from supply-chain and third-party vendors, the mitigation actions for vulnerabilities might take long time durations. These time durations are sufficient for adversaries

not only to identify critical targets within the infrastructure, but also to prepare custom-tailored attacks, which would cause operational disruptions on the running EV-oriented services on top of the infrastructure and could have cascading effects in the electrical grid.

Multiple attacks against the EV infrastructure are present in literature. Nevertheless, these attacks are not yet, to the best of our knowledge, systematically mapped to an architecture that allows to perform root cause analysis for the Tactics, Techniques and Procedures (TTPs) employed by adversaries. Additionally, the need to assess the attack impact on the EV infrastructure is required to reflect on the overall risk and consequences of EV-oriented cyber-attacks [3].

With several methods having been proposed in literature to cope with the vast threat surface of the EV infrastructure, such as intrusion detection systems [4], comparatively limited work exists for handling the distributed nature of the EV infrastructure and the cyber-attacks that are gradually becoming sophisticated through the integration with 5G networks [5]. Blockchain technology establishes a principal foundation

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to secure EV infrastructures and has been introduced to revolutionize the applications built on top of it [6].

By leveraging the inherent security and privacy preservation properties, commonly stemming from the consensus protocol, the smart contracts and the distributed network, blockchain technology serves as a counter-measure against cyber-attacks and enables trustless collaboration between heterogeneous stakeholders, including distribution system operators, EVs, EVCSs, and aggregators [7]. However, most of the current literature work typically focuses exclusively on the integration of blockchain technology for a single EV-oriented service that is usually EV charging [8]. For such integration, public and permissionless model structures are usually adopted, which trade security and privacy for openness, without considering the performance necessitated for complex EV infrastructures.

This article initially provides an analysis and taxonomy of the current state-of-the-art cyber-attack categories against the EV-oriented infrastructure, their categorization, as well as the Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures (TTPs) that are used based on standardized frameworks as MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise¹ and MITRE ICS ATT&CK². Then, the article surveys the most recent blockchain-enabled proposals for EV infrastructures to identify the best practices and integration patterns for addressing EV-oriented cyber-attacks. Finally, the article proposes a novel blockchain-enabled platform to protect and ensure the business continuity of the most common EV infrastructure services, i.e., EV charging, energy trading, and energy management. Specifically, the concrete contributions of this article are:

- Introduction of a concrete taxonomy for the existing threats in EV infrastructures that is also mapped to relevant TTPs based on the MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise and MITRE ICS ATT&CK frameworks.
- Implementation of a risk model to derive the severity of EV infrastructure threats and identify the most prominent amongst them.
- A detailed analysis of representative proposals covering recent literature work on the deployment of blockchain technologies in the most common EV infrastructure services, such as EV charging, energy trading, and energy management to extract the best practices and common patterns from blockchain integration for EV security.
- Design of the proposed architecture, with a range of cutting edge technologies, for the application of blockchain as a detection and mitigation mechanism in the EV infrastructure based on the risk model and the identified threats.
- Proof-of-concept validation of the proposed blockchain architecture in an EV-oriented testbed, allowing to detect the most prominent attacks against the EV infrastructure services.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. **Section 2** provides an overview of the EV infrastructure, the associated components and services as well of the blockchain technologies and their operating principles. Then, **Section 3** provides a threat taxonomy along with the affected EV infrastructure components based on the state-of-the-art cyber-attacks, categorizing them also according to the MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise and MITRE ICS ATT&CK TTPs. Based on the presented taxonomy, **Section 4** analyzes literature work that uses blockchain technologies to allow protection against the identified EV threats and allow business continuity in EV services. Following the presented analysis, **Section 5** proposes an architecture for tackling the EV infrastructure threats using blockchain technologies and details on the architectural integration in the most common EV services. Then, **Section 6** provides a proof-of-concept blockchain framework evaluation and discusses the experimental results in an EV-oriented testbed where the most prominent cyber-attacks are conducted. Finally, **Section 7** provides conclusions and future perspectives.

2. Preliminaries

This section provides an overview of the EV infrastructure and the most common services that reside on top of the infrastructure, as well as includes an introduction to the blockchain technology, platforms, and consensus protocol.

2.1. EV infrastructure

An overview of the components and offered services in EV-oriented services is depicted in **Fig. 1**. This representation is based on previous work [9]; however, it focuses on identifying the communication vectors that are used for the data exchange related to configurations, billing processes, and energy consumption information. The figure also provides all the individual components that are explained in the following section.

2.1.1. EV-oriented components

The components that are available in the EV infrastructure are mainly centered around the EVs and the EVCS, which provide the energy from the electrical grid to charge the EV batteries. The EVCS is comprised of sensors, controllers, power protection equipment, and also includes all the communication equipment that is used to handle the EV charging requests, such as the power electronics circuits and the metering devices.

Furthermore, the EVCS is comprised of the AC/DC inverter, the meter that measures the energy consumption, and the controller, including the firmware to allow data exchange with the CSMS system using the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) [10]. EVCS are distinguished in two main types: the Alternate Current (AC) chargers and the Direct Current (DC) chargers. The former provide standard charging capabilities, and the EV uses the OnBoard Charger (OBC) to convert the current capacity provided from the electrical grid from AC to DC within the EV and then use it to charge the batteries. The latter provide fast charging capabilities as the energy is converted from AC to DC through an inverter within the EVCS, and upon charging, it is directly provided to the EV batteries, without the intervention of the OBC.

Another component that is crucial and part of the EV architecture is the CSMS. The CSMS is responsible for controlling, monitoring, and performing maintenance in all the EV charging stations as well as the resolution of faults or issues in them [10]. Furthermore, it can also obtain remote diagnostics from the EVCSs and hence have real-time availability, operating status, and also obtain audit logs from them. For these reasons, it is often considered as a single point of failure in the EV infrastructure, since if an operational or cybersecurity issue occurs on the CSMS, it will automatically disrupt the EV infrastructure and its business operation.

There are further components that are important for the EV-oriented infrastructure, but do not provide the main infrastructure functionality. These components allow electrical grid stability by providing the required energy for the operation of the infrastructure. Such components include on-site PVs, the Battery Storage System (BSS) components for providing the energy surplus that is required for transferring the energy to the EVs.

All the infrastructure components lie in the responsibility of the Charge Point Operator (CPO). The CPO is hence responsible for setting up the EVCS, making them available, and providing remote management, fault identification and resolution, as well as diagnostics on them. This process is facilitated by the OCPP [10], which is used by the CPOs to allow a standardized way of interacting with the EVCS using commands that are implemented by each manufacturer.

2.1.2. EV services

This section provides an overview of the services that are offered on top of the EV infrastructure components and are managed by the e-mobility Managed Service Providers (eMSPs). Moreover, each service is

¹ <https://attack.mitre.org/matrices/enterprise/>

² <https://attack.mitre.org/matrices/ics/>

Fig. 1. A high-level overview of an EV infrastructure.

linked with different infrastructure components, and hence, the component availability is a prerequisite for providing the service.

Specifically, there are multiple services offered within the EV-oriented infrastructure, but within the scope of this work, the focus was on the most commonly employed by the eMSPs that are also the most prominent ones in both literature and business operations, such as EV charging, energy trading, and energy management. However, the work can be easily expanded if further eMSP services become prominent. The services are accordingly presented, focusing on their operational functionality, but also on the involved EV infrastructure components.

EV charging. EV charging is the main service that is provided by the CPO and managed by the eMSP. This service is linked to starting and stopping a charging session, providing the required authorization for allowing the session to be initiated. Each EV charging transaction starts with an initial authorization that is performed by the CSMS. Based on this initial authorization, the eMSP allows the transaction to start. At the end of the transaction, the total energy that is consumed is calculated for billing purposes.

Specifically, the CPO is responsible for providing the availability of the infrastructure and the eMSP for clearing the transactions by calculating the total energy that is charged. Such a calculation can be performed by obtaining energy consumption measurements (i.e., Current, Voltage, Active Power in kW, and reactive power in VAR) through the smart meter that resides in each EVCS.

Conventional payment procedures for EV charging usually involve multiple intermediaries, leading to complicated and time-intensive transactions. Therefore, security and trust are imperative in EV charging systems, particularly for the verification of the EVCS authenticity, ensuring fair pricing, and protecting user data.

Overall, the EV infrastructure components that are involved in this service, based on the Fig. 1 architecture, are the EV, the EVCS, and the CSMS.

Energy trading. Energy trading is another service that is provided by the electrical grid and is related to EVs through the energy that is bought,

or sold, or exchanged to optimize costs. This allows the grid to optimize the overall electricity costs, but also to increase its stability. Furthermore, this also links to shifting the surplus energy that is available from one electrical network segment to another. Such surplus energy shifting requires advanced algorithms for performing the calculations in terms of demand-response scenarios [11].

Based on the complexity of the energy trading process, the EV infrastructure components that are involved in the trading service, based on the overview of Fig. 1, are the EVs, the EVCS, the ADMS platform, and the transmission operator systems, because they cover the energy-oriented transactions that are performed.

Energy management. Managing the electricity that is exchanged between the EVs and the electricity grid is quite challenging, and it falls into the category of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) that is also incorporating Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) technologies [10]. Additionally, V2X is linked with the interconnection of all the entities of the EV infrastructure to allow automation capabilities for handling the energy demand and response [11]. A central point for energy management services is how to facilitate the exchange of the energy surplus from or to sectors that the EVs are directly or indirectly connected with, such as transport systems or urban environments, including households and enterprise buildings, as well as industrial areas. Moreover, V2X also includes the interactions between different EVs as well as with further energy management systems.

Furthermore, the components of the EV infrastructure that contribute to the energy management service are mostly linked with third-party vendors, as many CPOs and eMSPs are using known vendors for hardware or software for the EVCS, but also the CSMS component, to include them in their offered EV energy management service. The main issue, however, is that third-party vendors might include unintentional vulnerabilities in the firmware of the EVCS as described in Nasr et al. [12], or the CSMS software, or even the hardware. These vulnerabilities may be exploited by adversaries to gain initial access to the EV infrastructure. Furthermore, upon discovering the introduced vulnera-

Table 1
Blockchain technology's characteristics.

Blockchain Platform	Network Type	Consensus Protocol	Fault Tolerance	Smart Contracts
Bitcoin	Permissionless	PoW	<50% comput. power	Bitcoin Script, Miniscript
Kovan (Ethereum)	Permissionless	PoA	BFT: $2f + 1$	Solidity
Hyperledger Fabric	Permissioned	Raft Kafka PBFT	CFT: $2t + 1$ BFT: $3f + 1$	Go, Node.js, Java
EOSIO	Hybrid ^a	DPoS	BFT: $3f + 1$	C++
NEO	Permissioned	DBFT	BFT: $3f + 1$	C#, Kotlin

^a Both permissioned and permissionless.

bilities, patching or creating new firmware might be a time-consuming process.

Most of the EV infrastructure components of Fig. 1 are involved in this service, including the EVs, the EVCS, the Battery Storage, the On-site PV, the Aggregator, the ADMS platform and the transmission operator systems.

2.2. Blockchain technology

Blockchain has recently received significant attention in various scientific fields, due to its technological innovation capabilities, but also by inherently enhancing security and privacy. Realized as a sovereign root-of-trust to distribute information between entities, a sequence of records and a continuum of blocks is established [13]. Blockchain technology essentially uses a decentralized and immutable service, without the need for a centralized entity for preserving records and agreements of mutually distrustful entities. While this constitutes a main technology characteristic, its unique security properties are also envisioned to revolutionize the applications built on top of it.

Blockchains can be separated into different networks, contingent on the access control policies provisioned to the network nodes. In contrast to permissionless networks, in which any node can be part of the network, permissioned networks can be classified into private and public, with blockchain nodes that are identifiable and can be liable for any malicious action. Blockchain technology is also enhanced with segments of code, referred to as "smart contracts". The smart contracts are commonly used to compel adherence in operations that are accredited by the entire network, to automate access control policies, but also to verify that the agreements between the network's nodes are executed under certain conditions.

Amongst the various processes incorporated in a blockchain network, the transaction's total order is established via the consensus protocol, which is a key process to facilitate the overall security of a blockchain network. The consensus can be tolerant against system crashes, i.e., *Crash Fault Tolerant* (CFT), such as Kafka [14] and Raft [15], where the blockchain network can tolerate many crashing nodes (t); or against malicious behavior, i.e., *Byzantine Fault Tolerant* (BFT), such as *Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerant* (PBFT) [16], *Proof-of-Authority* (PoA) [17], *Delegated Proof-of-Stake* (DPoS) [18] and *Delegated Byzantine Fault Tolerant* (DBFT) [19]. In such scenarios, the blockchain network can tolerate several malicious nodes (f); or against malicious nodes with computational power, as occurs in the *Proof-of-Work* (PoW) [20].

Therefore, the architectural choices of a consensus protocol can significantly impact the blockchain network's security and consequently the application built on top of it [6]. For this reason, the most prominent consensus protocols and blockchain platforms, commonly found to be integrated in EV infrastructures, along with their architectural characteristics, are presented in Table 1.

3. Cybersecurity threat landscape and risk analysis of EV infrastructures

This section describes an initial threat assessment of the EV-oriented infrastructure and then proceeds to provide a risk assessment methodology to derive the most prominent threats in the infrastructure.

3.1. Threat assessment

The threats that are targeting the EV infrastructure, as well as the corresponding services in it (detailed in the previous sections), are hereby grouped into categories in Tables 2, 3. More specifically, the table provides a structured and detailed mapping of cybersecurity threats across the EV ecosystem. The Table was constructed through a comprehensive threat modeling process that integrates academic literature, industry reports, and real-world case studies. The objective was to provide a clear understanding of how different components within the EV infrastructure are vulnerable to cyber-attacks and how those attacks align with well-established adversarial behavior models.

Moreover, Tables 2 and 3 are those of a typical EV infrastructure ecosystem architecture: EVs, charging infrastructure, communication channels, grid infrastructure, energy systems, etc. Within these categories, relevant subcategories are presented (onboard system, firmware, servers, etc.), in parallel with threat vector, through which exposure to risk may take place. These vectors represent technical entry points or design weaknesses (e.g. inadequate authentication mechanisms, physical interfaces, insecure communication protocols, etc.). Moreover, each vector is also connected to an attack example, where the target of the attacker or his action is described (e.g. introducing malware, privilege escalation, impersonation, data tampering, etc.).

The basis for the structure of the tables is the MITRE ATT&CK framework, which provides a standardized taxonomy of attack tactics and techniques. Each attack type (even if not observed in the real world yet), was connected with one or more specific official MITRE technique IDs (also included in the table's columns, e.g., T0857 for unauthorized firmware modification). In the last columns of the tables, we have included specific mitigation measures for each threat (also marked with their official IDs in the framework - M-codes), the application of which may lead to the reduction of attack surface or the prevention of exploitation.

For methodological purposes, a combination of the two matrices, MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise and MITRE Industrial Control Systems (ICS) was decided. On the one hand, we used ICS matrix for the systems which are directly connected to physical infrastructure and which are part of the Operational Technology (OT): EVs, charging infrastructure, network infrastructure, Utility Control Systems (UCS), Energy Storage Systems (BSS), and Energy Installation Systems (OES). These systems are, in principle, related to embedded platforms, real-time requirements and physical control interfaces, which face threats extensively described in the ICS framework, such as unauthorized signal injection, firmware tampering and SCADA manipulation. It should be underlined that this specific fra-

Table 2
Cyber-attacks on EV infrastructures.

#	Reference	Component	Threat Vector	Attack Type	MITRE ID	MITRE Countermeasure
Electric Vehicles	[21–33]	EV Onboard Systems	External Interfaces (OBD-II, USB, SD)	Malware Injection, Privilege Escalation	T0806, T0822	M0937, M0807, M0930, M0813, M0942, M0927
	[34–38]	Firmware Updates	Weak Protocols (e.g., black encryption)	Unauthorized Firmware Modification	T0857	M0947, M0946, M0945, M0802, M0804, M0801, M0813, M0807, M0930, M0937
	[21,39–45]	Diagnostics Systems	External Interfaces (OBD-II, USB)	Injection of Malicious Code	T0864	M0949, M0947, M0941, M0930, M0951
	[22,27,46–63,116]	V2C Communications	Weak Protocols (e.g., insecure communication) Insufficient Encryption	Spoofing, Data Interception, Protocol Downgrade Attack Replay Attacks	T0856, T0830 T0830	M0802, M0937, M0807, M0930, M0813, M0947, M0942, M0931, M0810, M0814 M0947, M0802, M0942, M0931, M0930, M0810, M0813, M0814
	[42,58,60,64–73]	EV Infotainment System	External Interfaces (Wi-Fi, Cellular, Bluetooth) Third-Party Apps Data Interfaces (USB, SD Card)	Exploitation of Weak Authentication Mechanisms in Infotainment Systems, Remote Code Execution Software Vulnerabilities Physical Access	T0866 T0862 T0847	M0802, M0808, M0806, M0813, M0948, M0942, M0950, M0930, M0926, M0919, M0951, M0916 M0947, M0945, M0817, M0951, M0916 M0942, M0934, M0928
Charging Infrastructure	[68,74–80]	Charging Station Firmware	Weak Protocols	Insecure Firmware Updates, Exploitation of Firmware Vulnerabilities	T0857	M0801, M0947, M0946, M0945, M0802, M0808, M0941, M0937, M0804, M0807, M0930, M0813, M0951
	[81–84]	Charging Station Hardware	Physical Access (e.g., USB, Ethernet)	Bypassing Access Control in Charging Station Interfaces, Hardware Sabotage via Physical Manipulation of Charging Components	T0847, T0879	M0942, M0934, M0928, M0805, M0807, M0812
	[68,74,80,83–88]	Charging Station Software	Software Vulnerabilities (e.g., OCPP) Insufficient Input Validation Communication with EVs	Man-in-the-Middle Attack Leading to Data Manipulation Injection Attacks Weak Protocols	T0830 T0807 T0830	M0947, M0802, M0942, M0931, M0930, M0810, M0813, M0814 M0942, M0938, M0807 M0947, M0802, M0942, M0931, M0930, M0810, M0813, M0814
Communication Channel	[74,83,89–95]	EVSE-CSMS Communication	Unencrypted Communication Links in OCPP Authentication Issues Data Pathway Exploitation	Eavesdropping Weak Authentication Mechanisms Replay Attacks	T1557 T1078 T1557	M1042, M1041, M1037, M1035, M1031, M1030, M1017, M0802 M1036, M1015, M1013, M1032, M1027, M1026, M1018, M1017 M1042, M1041, M1037, M1035, M1031, M1030, M1017
	[67,80,89,96–107]	Wireless Communications	External Interfaces	Data Exfiltration via Wireless Signal Interception, Key Extraction via Wireless Side-Channel Attacks, Denial of Service via Jamming of Wireless Communication Channels	T1020, T1203, T1499.001	M1048, M1050, M1051, M1037, M0805
	[60,74,83,89,104,106–111]	Communication Protocols	Weak Protocols and Encryption	Protocol Misconfiguration, Protocol Exploitation, Unauthorized Command Injection	T1001.003, T1210, T1059	M1031, M1048, M1042, M1050, M1030, M1026, M1019, M1051, M1016
BSS ^a	[112–115,117–124]	Energy Storage	Physical Access	Battery Overload Induced via Manipulated Charging Cycles Injection of Malicious Data to Corrupt Battery Management System (BMS)	T0831, T0832	M0802, M0953, M0810

^a Battery Storage Systems.

mework has been formulated to analyze cyber-physical threats to critical infrastructure.

Conversely, the MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise matrix was applied to systems operating within traditional Information Technology (IT) environments, where attacks target digital assets through conventional means such as web protocols, authentication mechanisms, and application logic. Specifically, Communication Channels, Cloud-

based CSMS, and Cloud and Storage Systems (CSS) fall into this category. These systems are typically managed using enterprise-grade tools and policies for identity management, application security, and incident response. Therefore, they are best modeled using the Enterprise matrix, which captures techniques like credential dumping, session hijacking, API exploitation, and server misconfiguration.

Table 3
Cyber-attacks on EV ecosystems (continued).

#	Reference	Component	Threat Vector	Attack Type	MITRE ID	MITRE Countermeasure
CSMS	[67,74,102,125–132]	Cloud-Based	Authentication Issues	Public API Exploits, Data Manipulation	T1133, T1565.001	M1042, M1035, M1032, M1030, M1041, M1029, M1022
	[67,74,89,133,134]	CSMS APIs	API Rate Limiting Failures	Resource Exhaustion (DDoS)	T1499	M1037, M1030, M1029
	[74,84,104,109,135]	CSMS Backend	System Configuration Issues	Weak Firewall Rules, DDoS	T1562.004, T1499	M1047, M1022, M1024, M1018, M1037
	[74,111,133,136,137]	Server	Server Misconfigurations Privilege Abuse	Data Breach Administrative Exploitation	T1530 T1068	M1047, M1041, M1037, M1032, M1022, M1018 M1048, M1038, M1050, M1019, M1051
	[80,84,86,104–106,111,133,138–148]	Mobile Applications	Software Vulnerabilities	Weak Session Management, Credential Theft, Data Injection, API Token Misuse, Session Hijacking, Phishing Links in App	T1649, T1555, T1059, T1528, T1557, T1566	M1015, M1047, M1042, M1041, M1027, M1026, M1038, M1033, M1018
Grid Infrastructure	[126,149–153]	V2G Communication	Insecure Authentication in V2G Protocols	Grid Overload Attack via Manipulated V2G Protocol Commands, Energy Theft Exploiting Weak Metering and Billing Mechanisms	T0855, T0882	M0802, M0937, M0807, M0930, M0813, M0818, M0803, M0941, M0809, M0922
	[102,136,154–181]	Electrical Grid Systems	Outdated Security Standards in Grid Communication Protocols	Network Protocol Exploitation, Sybil Attacks	T0866, T0884	M0948, M0942, M0950, M0930, M0926, M0919, M0951, M0916, M0937, M0807, M0931, M0920
			Signal Manipulation	Signal Injection	T0855	M0802, M0937, M0807, M0930, M0813, M0818
			Data Manipulation	Data Manipulation	T0832	M0802, M0953, M0810
			Network Topology Manipulation	Grid Disruption via Injection of False Communication Signals	T0831	M0802, M0953, M0810
[160,182–187]	Substation Network	Physical Access	Grid Manipulation via Direct Circuit Breaker Tampering	T0879	M0805, M0807, M0812	
Utility Control Systems	[67,74,101,106,188–196]	Authentication System, SCADA Server, Control Room Hardware)	Authentication Issues	Privilege Abuse	T0859	M0801, M0936, M0915, M0913, M0947, M0937, M0932, M0927, M0926, M0918
			Vulnerable SCADA Systems	Data Manipulation	T0832	M0802, M0953, M0810
			Physical Access Exploits	Sabotage	T0879	M0805, M0807, M0812
CSS ^b	[75,101,106,195,197–206]	Cloud Servers	Authentication Issues	Credential Dumping and Exploitation of Weak Passwords, Data Breach	T1003, T1078	M1015, M1040, M1043, M1041, M1028, M1027, M1026, M1025, M1017, M1036, M1013, M1032, M1018
			Server Misconfigurations	Credential Dumping	T1003	M1015, M1040, M1043, M1041, M1028, M1027, M1026, M1025, M1017
OES ^c	[66,80,102,106,155,158,163,195,207–215]	Photovoltaic (PV) Panels	External Interfaces	Solar System Manipulation, Power Theft, Disabling of Panels, Energy Interruption	T0831, T0882, T0814	M0802, M0953, M0810, M0803, M0941, M0809, M0922, M0815

^a Utility Control Systems

^b Cloud and Storage Systems

^c On-site Energy Systems.

On the other hand, we chose to use the MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise matrix for the systems that operate within conventional IT environments, where digital assets are targeted through typical methods, e.g., web protocols, authentication mechanisms, application logic, etc. Thus, the matrix was used for the categories Communication Channels, cloud-based CSMS, and Cloud and Storage Systems (CSS). Such systems are usually configured through enterprise-level tools and are based on

rather standard policies (e.g., identity management, applications security, incident response, etc.), thus MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise matrix was preferred, since it covers credential theft, session hijacking, API exploitation, misconfigured servers or other similar techniques.

We strongly consider that the hybrid model we have adopted, that combines the two frameworks of MITRE ATT&CK, Enterprise and ICS, helps us perform a threat assessment which is far more accurate and

comprehensive. This is a basic requirements by the modern form of the EV ecosystem, which incorporates both IT and OT systems. This combination offers precision and flexibility, which are of utmost importance, since we can clearly distinguish the context within which an attack appears (e.g., a web-facing API vs a control circuit in a charging station). In such way, we ensure that the countermeasures proposed fully align with existing operational technicalities of each system. Additionally, our proposed mitigation plans are based on IT cybersecurity and industrial security best practices.

3.1.1. Electric vehicles

The EV infrastructure (including onboard systems, firmware, communication protocols, and infotainment interfaces, etc.), is exposed to several vulnerabilities. Cyber attackers are able to exploit external interfaces (e.g., OBD-II, USB, SD slots, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, cellular connections, etc.) to inject malicious software, manipulate ECUs, intercept sessions, as well as execute various forms of attacks, such as Man-in-The-Middle (MiTM), spoofing, and replay attacks. [21,22,26,58]. Vulnerabilities are also related to the Controller Area Network (CAN) protocol, since it lacks encryption and authentication [49,52,216].

3.1.2. Charging infrastructure

During the firmware update processes, several risks are also present, mainly due to encryption weaknesses, authentication issues, and integrity checks. This means that ECUs could be exposed to unauthorized alterations during Over-The-Air (OTA) updates [34,37]. The integration of third-party applications and complex infotainment systems further increases the attack surface, exposing vehicles to phishing, malware, and remote code execution attacks [65,67,106].

3.1.3. Communication channels

EV charging stations face significant cybersecurity risks due to vulnerabilities in communication protocols, software, and hardware. Weak authentication, inadequate input validation, and insecure protocols, such as OCPP, enable attacks such as MiTM, public API exploitation, and firmware manipulation [74,75,77,78,80]. Malik and Anwar identify vulnerabilities in management systems, including those from Schneider Electric [68], while studies highlight risks of oscillatory load attacks that threaten grid stability [80]. Physical threats also pose risks, as attackers can exploit access points like USB and Ethernet ports to sabotage operations or manipulate hardware [81,83,84]. Weak input validation exposes systems to SQL Injection and Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) attacks [86,87].

Cloud-based CSMS introduce additional risks, since poor authentication and misconfiguration can result in credential dumping and data breaches [127–129,132]. Researchers underline the need for stronger prevention measures [such as multi-factor authentication (MFA), secure firmware updates, real-time monitoring, robust input validation] [130,131]. Despite the fact that solar charging is explored in certain studies [88], the urgent need for layered, robust security measures is overall prioritized, towards safeguarding EV charging systems.

Vulnerabilities in the EV charging ecosystem, mainly because of non-secure communication protocols, weak encryption, and authentication issues, expose systems to MiTM, replay, and command injection attacks [74,89,90]. External interfaces, such as USB, wireless, and cloud communication channels, which are not properly secured, may result in data exfiltration, jamming, the creation of botnets, as well as side-channel attacks. This means that system integrity and grid stability are at risk [80,84,96,103,104].

3.1.4. Charging station management systems

The most important risks that the CSMS and the mobile applications face are related to weak authentication, misconfigurations, and insecure communication protocols. By exploiting these, cyber attackers can launch several types of attacks: MiTM, Distributed Denial of

Service (DDoS), replay attacks, manipulation of APIs, sessions hijacking. These may also lead to unauthorized access to sensitive data [67,74,89,102,127]. Indicative mitigation measures proposed are robust authentication, MFA, proper firewall configurations, secure API design, as well as continuous monitoring [130,131]. Credential theft, phishing, and cloud service manipulation could take place since mobile applications are used [80,104,106]. Research underlines that early threat detection may be supported by blockchain frameworks and machine learning techniques [144,146,147].

3.1.5. Grid infrastructure

The cyber risks that the V2G systems and the broader electrical grid ecosystem face are connected to insecure communication protocols, weak authentication, and the usage of outdated standards. Because of vulnerabilities in V2G authentication, access without authorization, grid manipulation, relay attacks, and energy trading fraud is possible [126,149–152]. In such circumstances, attackers use techniques such as signal manipulation, False Data Injection (FDI), and network topology manipulation, which can cause the disruption of power management or state estimation processes. Research underlines that the usage of IEC 61850 in the grid ecosystem [substations, Distributed Energy Resources (DERs), and feeder substations] gives the opportunity to attackers to tamper with circuit breakers, compromise protection functionalities, and disrupt grid operations [136,157,160,161,166,171,182,183].

Strengthening security frameworks (including in principle network segmentation, continuous monitoring, and machine learning-based intrusion detection) is crucial for the protection of the integrity, privacy, and reliability of V2G systems, feeder substations, and the overall electrical grid [146,177,179–181,184–187].

3.1.6. Utility control systems

Utility Control Systems (UCS), including SCADA systems, are at risk originating both from insider threats and physical access exploits. Attackers take advantage of vulnerabilities such as weak authentication, improper access controls, and physical interfaces, so as to cause service disruptions, manipulate operations, or tamper with data [188,190,194,195]. Mitigation strategies include stronger access controls, continuous monitoring, and real-time intrusion detection. Compliance with ISO / SAE 21434 is also underlined [106,191]. Additionally, security tools based on AI have been proposed for enhancing defense. [101,192,193]. As the EV ecosystem's expansion continues, comprehensive threat analysis and risk assessments are necessary [67,196].

3.1.7. Cloud & storage systems

Weak authentication, credential dumping, and misconfiguration are vulnerabilities exposing cloud servers, which are typically used in EV infrastructures. Attackers regularly exploit poor password and credential management in order to gain unauthorized access, which further results to data breaches and disruptions [197,198,203,204]. For the protection of cloud-based systems, researchers highlight the need for measures such as continuous monitoring, secure authentication (e.g., MFA, behavioral biometrics), stronger configuration management, and auditing of third-parties [199–202,205,206].

3.1.8. Battery storage systems

Battery Storage Systems (BSS) face major risks from physical access attacks. Attackers may manipulate charging cycles or inject false data into Battery Management Systems (BMS). These could lead to thermal runaway, system failures, or even cause the reduction of battery lifespan [112–115,122,123]. Researchers underscore advanced mitigation solutions, including up-to-date energy management strategies, continuous monitoring and AI-based analytics. These measures enhance grid stability and can support the prevention of overloads [118,119,124].

3.1.9. On-site energy systems

Non-secure communication protocols and the existence of external interfaces expose PV panels in On-site Energy Systems (OES). Attackers can inject false data, perform Denial of Service (DoS) attacks, or disable PV operations, potentially disrupting energy supply for EV charging [207,208]. The use of intelligent inverters and computational intelligence increases attack surfaces, requiring secure authentication, ISO SAE 21434-compliant frameworks, and interface protection [80,106,155,158,163,210,212,213,215].

3.2. Threat analysis

The proposed threat-assessment framework builds on a decade of work in connected-vehicle security evaluation. Initially, Kong et al. proposed systematic methods for security evaluation of connected cars, using weighted CIA scoring and attack-tree analysis to quantify likelihood in smart vehicles [217,218]. These early studies demonstrated that a consistent scoring scheme across multiple threat categories enables comparability, while attack-tree mathematics provides a defensible route to likelihood estimation.

Recent EV-specific frameworks also motivate the followed approach in this article. Sourmelis and Meng [219] applied the NIST Cybersecurity Framework (CSF) to EVs, emphasizing structured scoping, identification of assets, and repeatable assessment cycles. Shirvani et al. [220] proposed a comprehensive risk assessment methodology for EV ecosystems based on STRIDE, showing that EV security can be systematically profiled across charging, software, connectivity, and autonomy. Additional alignment with these practices is performed by combining STRIDE / MITRE tagging with NIST-style scoping and a calibrated risk matrix.

At the subsystem level, Zhang et al. introduced a Cyber Security Evaluation Framework (CSEF) for in-vehicle ECUs and demonstrated that pure CIA scoring tends to underestimate safety-of-life risks in safety-critical automotive subsystems [221]. This served as a motivation to add an explicit *human safety axis* (H), scored on the same five-level scale (Negligible to Critical) as CIA, and a safety override rule, ensuring that critical threats with life-threatening consequences are not down-classified.

Furthermore, resilience considerations inform the design of the risk model that is presented in the following section. EV charging ecosystems are *system-of-systems* where faults can cascade across organizational and technology boundaries (e.g., CSMS! → Charging Infrastructure fleets or EV! → grid DR interfaces). To reflect such fleet-level or cross-domain effects observed in EV risk profiling and NIST-style scoping, we introduce a modest *cascading effect* (k) that inflates risk when lateral spread is credible [219,220]. This acknowledges that systemic cascading impact can exceed the direct severity of a single compromised asset.

In summary, the proposed approach in this article integrates multiple strands of prior research. From Kong's smart-car work, the CIA scoring and attack-tree likelihoods are inherited [217,218], but extend them with calibrated five-level scales for CIA, H , Impact, and Severity, and probability-based five-level scales for Likelihood. From NIST-CSF-based EV analysis [219], this work considers the structured scoping and profiling of assets. From Shirvani et al.'s taxonomy [220], the STRIDE tagging and risk-matrix interpretation are adopted. From ECU evaluation frameworks [221], insights are inherited as the fact that explicit safety-of-life axes are necessary.

Moreover, the literature on EV security profiling and NIST-style scoping treats the ecosystem as a system-of-systems [219,220]. Therefore, the potential *cascading effect* is modeled explicitly via k . Together, these elements yield a methodology that is (i) transparent and auditable, (ii) comparable across domains, and (iii) calibrated to the human-safety and systemic risks unique to EV ecosystems, with risk values consistently normalized to the [0-5] range.

While several risk assessment approaches for EV-related systems have been proposed in the literature, most of them focus on isolated

Table 4

Qualitative levels (five-level scales) used in the risk evaluation.

Metric	Representative anchors (1–5)
C, I, A, H	Negligible / Low / Moderate / High / Critical
L	Rare / Unlikely / Possible / Likely / Certain

subsystems, apply qualitative analyses, or rely on partial frameworks such as CIA or STRIDE in isolation. In contrast, the approach adopted in this work provides a unified, ecosystem-wide risk assessment that integrates a comprehensive EV threat taxonomy with joint MITRE ATT&CK Enterprise and MITRE ICS ATT&CK mapping, an extended CIA model including human safety, and cascading impact considerations across interconnected EV domains. To the best of our knowledge, this specific combination is not jointly addressed by existing EV security risk assessment studies.

3.2.1. Risk model

Table 4 defines the ordinal scales used in this work. Each threat is evaluated along five axes: *Confidentiality* (C), *Integrity* (I), *Availability* (A), *Human Safety* (H), and *Likelihood* (L) of successful exploitation. All axes are scored on a 1–5 scale with explicit anchors, ensuring repeatability and comparability across systems.

The CIA dimensions capture the traditional security triad: loss of confidentiality refers to unauthorized disclosure of information. Then, loss of integrity refers to tampering with commands, data, or telemetry, and loss of availability refers to partial or complete DoS. The additional human safety axis (H) reflects the cyber-physical nature of EV ecosystems, where compromises of firmware, protocols, or control logic may directly endanger passengers, the public, or grid stability. Without this explicit dimension, life-critical impacts would often be underestimated.

The first step in the proposed risk model is to compute a weighted CIA impact score. Because the relative importance of confidentiality, integrity, and availability differs across domains, a system-specific weight vector is defined (w_C, w_I, w_A) such that $w_C + w_I + w_A = 1$. The impact of each threat is then given by:

$$\text{Imp}_{\text{CIA}} = w_C \cdot C + w_I \cdot I + w_A \cdot A. \quad (1)$$

Default weights are (0.20, 0.50, 0.30) for EVs, charging infrastructure, grid, and UCS (safety-critical domains); (0.25, 0.45, 0.30) for communications; and (0.45, 0.35, 0.20) for cloud services and CSMS. This produces Imp_{CIA} values in the range [1, 5], interpreted on the same five-level scale (Negligible to Critical).

The weighting scheme adopted in this work should be understood as a set of pragmatic default values, selected to reflect common risk assessment practices in safety-critical and cyber-physical environments rather than as fixed or universally optimal coefficients. In the context of EVs, charging infrastructure, grid systems, and utility control systems, greater emphasis is placed on integrity and availability, since violations in these dimensions may directly compromise safe operation, physical assets, or overall grid stability. This choice is in line with NIST CSF-oriented EV risk assessment methodologies and STRIDE-based analyses, which consistently identify tampering and DoS attacks as more critical than pure information disclosure in such environments [219,220].

Additionally, prior studies on automotive Electronic Control Units (ECUs) have shown that conventional CIA-based scoring tends to underestimate safety-of-life implications, thereby motivating both the prioritization of integrity and availability and the explicit inclusion of a safety dimension in the risk model [221–226]. The chosen weights give a reasonable starting point. They can be altered for different deployment cases without changing the structure or the general use of the model and without affecting its applicability.

To reflect both technical and human consequences, the CIA impact is then combined with the safety score H into an overall severity:

$$\text{Sev} = 0.7 \cdot \text{Imp}_{\text{CIA}} + 0.3 \cdot H. \quad (2)$$

This method makes sure that safety-critical threats are highlighted but does not hide technical factors. Severity stays on the same five-level scale, so it is easy to compare risks across different areas.

Likelihood is treated as an evidence-based measure rather than a probabilistic forecast. This approach aligns with the guidance of NIST SP 800-30, which explicitly allows qualitative, ordinal scales when empirical frequency data are unavailable, and with CVSS-style exploitability scoring, which aggregates observable factors into discrete levels. In practice, likelihood is interpreted in terms of how often an attack has already been demonstrated or reported. Because empirical incident data for EV infrastructures are scarce, this article relies on research papers, proof-of-concept exploits, and case studies as evidence of successful events. The conventional scale is retained - *Rare, Unlikely, Possible, Likely, Certain* -but reinterpreted as an ordinal, evidence-based anchor. Thus, the assignments of the risk model remain transparent and repeatable, while staying consistent with established risk assessment frameworks that emphasize structured expert judgment and documented evidence when statistical baselines are absent.

Because the EV ecosystem is a *system-of-systems*, a compromise may not remain local. To capture this possibility, a cascading effect multiplier is introduced, $k \in \{1.0, 1.1, 1.2\}$, which modestly amplifies the overall risk score. A value of $k = 1.0$ represents threats confined to a single component, such as a USB exploit in one vehicle; $k = 1.1$ denotes limited spread across connected peers, such as a weak EV \leftrightarrow charger protocol affecting a session; and $k = 1.2$ is reserved for credible fleet- or system-wide spread, such as a CSMS breach enabling remote manipulation of many EVCSs. The narrow range prevents cascading effects from dominating CIA and safety scores, while still recognizing the amplification potential of systemic threats.

The overall risk is then defined as the normalized product of likelihood, severity, and cascading effect:

$$\text{Risk} = \frac{1}{6} \cdot L \cdot \text{Sev} \cdot k. \quad (3)$$

Since $L \in [1, 5]$, $\text{Sev} \in [1, 5]$, and $k \leq 1.2$, the theoretical maximum of 30 is rescaled to 5. This normalization ensures that risks across all domains are directly comparable on a common $[0, 5]$ scale.

The risk scale is split into five categories, for interoperability purposes: Negligible ($[0, 1)$), Low ($[1, 2)$), Moderate ($[2, 3)$), High ($[3, 4)$), and Critical ($[4, 5]$). There is an extra safety condition: if $H \geq 4$ and $L \geq 3$, the threat is pushed to at least High, independently of the calculated score. This prevents serious safety issues from being rated too low just because their probability is low. In short, the model makes risk ratings clear and evidence-based. They remain consistent across systems as well as sensitive to both human safety and cascading effects.

3.2.2. Threat landscape by system

The overall threat analysis for each system is presented in Table 5. These results originate from the risk scores for each attack, which are calculated using our risk model. The detailed scores for each attack and category are in Table 6. Thus, the CIA ratings, $H, L, k, \text{Imp}_{\text{CIA}}, \text{Sev}, \text{risk}$, and class for every category-attack pair are included in the Table.

The results highlight some important points. First, the UCS and BSS systems have the highest mean risk scores (4.72 and 4.04). Their maximum risk values are in the Critical range. This is not surprising, since these systems are directly linked to safety-of-life functions. For example, attacks on SCADA or industrial controllers, or on battery management, can quickly cause physical harm to passengers, operators, or the power grid. The GRID system also has a high mean risk (3.64) and a Critical maximum (4.79). This means that, even though many threats to the grid are less common, the ones that do happen can spread widely and cause serious problems for the whole system.

On the other hand, threats to EVs and charging infrastructure (INFRA) have moderate mean risks (2.73 and 2.93). However, their highest risk values are still in the Critical range. This shows that not every attack on an EV is severe, but the most dangerous cases, such as firmware

Table 5

Aggregate risk per system under the proposed CIA + Safety framework (normalized to $[0, 5]$). The “Mean risk” column is the arithmetic mean of the per-threat risk scores reported in Table 6 for each system, while “Max risk” indicates the highest individual threat score observed within that system.

System	No. threats	Mean risk	Max risk
EV	12	2.73	4.37
INFRA	7	2.93	4.37
COMM	8	2.14	3.42
CSMS	8	2.44	3.46
GRID	5	3.64	4.79
UCS	3	4.72	4.79
CSS	2	2.04	2.46
BSS	2	4.04	4.58
OES	4	1.60	2.35

changes or fake software updates, can still be very serious. The communication (COMM) and CSMS categories have lower mean risk values (about 2.1 to 2.4). This suggests that many threats in these areas are limited in scope or easier to fix. Still, both categories have some High-risk cases, so it is important to design secure protocols and APIs.

Finally, the CSS and OES systems have the lowest overall risk, both in mean and maximum values. This is mostly because threats in these systems are usually about information, are local, or are easier to recover from. Overall, these results show that the CIA + Safety framework helps us see which systems need the most protection. UCS, BSS, and GRID should be the main focus for security investments. Systems like OES or CSS are not risk-free, but they can be managed with targeted and suitable controls.

Electric vehicles. The potential entry points for attacks in EVs are the ECUs, the CAN bus, diagnostic interfaces, OTA update mechanisms, Vehicle-to-Cloud (V2C) links, and infotainment platforms. Ensuring integrity here is the main issue, since safe operation depends on having accurate commands and telemetry. Availability is also important, as risks can range from charging refusal to reduced in-vehicle functions. Safety risks are highest when firmware or diagnostics are compromised ($H = 5$), since these attacks can directly threaten passengers (e.g., by disabling braking assistance, changing charging cycles, or installing malicious updates in critical driving components, etc.). These situations are considered Critical risks because they combine high severity, their likelihood is realistic, and they could even affect entire fleets if OTA channels were attacked.

On the other hand, threats such as passive data interception (low C , minimal H) or physical access to removable media (USB/SD) are considered less serious. In these cases, $k = 1.0$, as the impact is limited only to the affected vehicle and spread to others is practically not possible. Even if these attacks are still possible, they are classified as *Low risk*. In general, risks in the EV domain vary greatly i.e., from Critical risks, such as firmware and diagnostics compromise, to Low risks, such as local data interception. This highlights the need to distinguish between dangers that could threaten lives and those that are simply a minor issue.

EV charging infrastructure. Firmware and software weaknesses, insecure update channels, and misuse of the OCPP protocol are the primary concerns. Impacts affect both *integrity* (session state, tariff/metering) and *availability* (station outages). Safety is relevant ($H = 3-5$), especially when firmware compromise permits unsafe charging currents or disables protection mechanisms. Fleet-level cascading is credible when firmware or protocols are abused ($k = 1.2$), as one compromised station can be leveraged to attack many. This produces several Critical cases in Table 6. By contrast, localized events such as physical sabotage of a cabinet or bypassing of local access controls are assigned $k = 1.0$

Table 6

Per-attack risk evaluation under the proposed CIA + Safety framework. Risk is normalized to $[0, 5]$ as $\text{Risk} = (L \cdot \text{Sev} \cdot k) / 6$, with cascading effect k . Classification bands are defined as: Critical (4.0–5.0), High (3.0–3.9), Moderate (2.0–2.9), Low (1.0–1.9), and Negligible (0–0.9).

Category	Attack	C / I / A	H	L	k	Imp_{CIA}	Sev	Risk	Class
EV	Unauthorized Firmware Modification	2 / 5 / 4	5	5	1.2	4.10	4.37	4.37	Critical
	Malware Injection	2 / 5 / 3	5	5	1.2	3.80	4.16	4.16	Critical
	Privilege Escalation	2 / 5 / 3	5	5	1.2	3.80	4.16	4.16	Critical
	Injection of Malicious Code (Diagnostics)	3 / 4 / 3	5	5	1.2	3.50	3.95	3.95	High
	Replay Attacks (V2C)	1 / 4 / 3	2	5	1.1	3.10	2.77	2.54	Moderate
	Weak Authentication (Infotainment)	4 / 3 / 2	2	5	1.1	2.90	2.63	2.41	Moderate
	Spoofing (V2C)	2 / 4 / 3	3	4	1.1	3.30	3.21	2.35	Moderate
	Remote Code Execution (Infotainment)	4 / 4 / 3	3	4	1.0	3.70	3.49	2.33	Moderate
	Software Vulnerabilities (3rd-party apps)	3 / 4 / 3	2	4	1.0	3.50	3.05	2.03	Moderate
	Protocol Downgrade Attack (V2C)	3 / 4 / 3	3	3	1.0	3.50	3.35	1.68	Low
	Physical Access (USB/SD)	1 / 4 / 4	2	3	1.0	3.40	2.98	1.49	Low
	Data Interception (V2C)	5 / 2 / 1	1	4	1.0	2.30	1.91	1.27	Low
INFRA	Insecure Firmware Updates	1 / 5 / 4	5	5	1.2	4.10	4.37	4.37	Critical
	Exploited Firmware Vulnerabilities	1 / 5 / 4	5	5	1.2	4.10	4.37	4.37	Critical
	MITM → Data Manipulation (Software)	2 / 4 / 4	3	5	1.2	3.50	3.35	3.35	High
	Weak EVCS Protocols	1 / 4 / 4	3	4	1.1	3.40	3.28	2.41	Moderate
	Bypassing Access Control (Interfaces)	1 / 4 / 3	3	4	1.1	3.30	3.21	2.35	Moderate
	Injection (Insufficient Input Validation)	2 / 4 / 4	2	4	1.0	3.50	3.05	2.03	Moderate
	Hardware Sabotage (Physical)	1 / 4 / 4	3	3	1.0	3.40	3.28	1.64	Low
COMM	Replay Attacks	2 / 4 / 4	3	5	1.2	3.60	3.42	3.42	High
	Weak Authentication	2 / 4 / 3	3	5	1.2	3.30	3.21	3.21	High
	(Protocols) Unauthorized Command Injection	1 / 4 / 4	3	4	1.2	3.40	3.28	2.62	Moderate
	(Protocols) Misconfiguration / Exploitation	2 / 4 / 3	3	4	1.2	3.30	3.21	2.57	Moderate
	Jamming / DoS	1 / 2 / 5	2	4	1.0	3.10	2.77	1.85	Low
	Eavesdropping (Unencrypted OCPP)	3 / 2 / 1	1	4	1.0	2.30	1.91	1.27	Low
	(Wireless) Interception → Data Exfiltration	4 / 2 / 1	1	4	1.0	2.30	1.91	1.27	Low
	(Wireless) Side-Channel Key Extraction	4 / 2 / 1	1	3	1.0	2.30	1.91	0.95	Negligible
	CSMS	Data Manipulation (Auth Issues)	3 / 4 / 4	3	5	1.2	3.65	3.46	3.46
Public-API Exploits (IDOR/Injection)		2 / 4 / 4	2	5	1.1	3.60	3.12	2.86	Moderate
Admin Exploitation / Privilege Abuse		2 / 4 / 4	3	4	1.2	3.60	3.42	2.74	Moderate
(Mob) Weak Sessions / Credential Theft / Hijack		4 / 3 / 2	2	5	1.1	3.10	2.63	2.41	Moderate
Weak Firewall Rules → DDoS		1 / 2 / 5	2	4	1.2	3.10	2.77	2.22	Moderate
API Rate-Limit Failures → Resource Exhaustion		1 / 2 / 5	2	4	1.2	3.10	2.77	2.22	Moderate
(Mob) Data Injection / Token Misuse / Phishing		3 / 4 / 2	2	4	1.0	3.05	2.73	1.82	Low
Server Misconfig → Data Breach		4 / 3 / 3	1	4	1.0	3.40	2.68	1.79	Low
GRID	V2G Protocol Manipulation → Grid Overload	1 / 5 / 5	5	5	1.2	4.70	4.79	4.79	Critical
	Substation Physical Access → Breaker Tampering	1 / 5 / 5	5	5	1.2	4.70	4.79	4.79	Critical
	Smart-Grid Signal Injection / Data Tampering	1 / 5 / 4	5	4	1.2	4.40	4.58	3.66	High
	Lateral Propagation (Poor Segmentation)	1 / 4 / 4	4	4	1.2	4.10	4.07	3.26	High
	Energy Theft (Weak Metering/Billing)	2 / 4 / 2	2	4	1.0	2.80	2.56	1.71	Low
UCS	Auth Issues → Privilege Abuse	1 / 5 / 5	5	5	1.2	4.70	4.79	4.79	Critical
	Vulnerable SCADA → Data Manipulation	1 / 5 / 5	5	5	1.2	4.70	4.79	4.79	Critical
	Physical Access → Sabotage	1 / 4 / 5	5	5	1.2	4.40	4.58	4.58	Critical
CSS	Cloud-Server Auth Issues → Cred Dump / Breach	4 / 3 / 3	1	5	1.1	3.40	2.68	2.46	Moderate
	Server Misconfig → Credential Dumping	4 / 3 / 2	1	4	1.0	3.05	2.43	1.62	Low
BSS	Malicious Data Injection to Corrupt BMS	1 / 5 / 4	5	5	1.2	4.40	4.58	4.58	Critical
	Battery Overload via Manipulated Charging Cycles	1 / 4 / 5	5	4	1.2	4.10	4.37	3.50	High
OES	Solar-System Manipulation	1 / 3 / 4	3	4	1.1	3.30	3.21	2.35	Moderate
	Energy Interruption	1 / 2 / 4	2	4	1.1	2.90	2.63	1.93	Low
	Disabling of Panels	1 / 2 / 4	1	3	1.0	2.90	2.33	1.17	Low
	Power Theft	1 / 3 / 2	1	3	1.0	2.35	1.95	0.97	Negligible

because the damage remains isolated, resulting in Low classifications. Thus, charging infrastructure threats are highly polarized: local attacks remain Low–Moderate, while protocol- or firmware-level exploits can quickly escalate to Critical.

Communication channels. Weak authentication, replay, MITM, and jamming dominate this domain. The main consequences are on *integrity* and *availability*, e.g., falsified commands or service interruptions. Safety impacts are generally moderate ($H = 1-3$) since communication attacks usually disrupt service rather than directly endanger life. Propagation is uneven: when communication links between Charging Infrastructure and CSMS are exploited, $k = 1.2$ is applied, since the attack can scale from one session to many stations. These threats often score High, de-

spite moderate H , because of their ability to affect many users simultaneously. In contrast, threats such as passive eavesdropping or side-channel key extraction remain strictly local ($k = 1.0$) and are therefore classified as *Low risk*, despite their technical sophistication. This duality illustrates that communication risks are more sensitive to cascading potential than to raw severity.

Charging station management systems. Threats include API abuse, weak sessions, misconfigurations, and mobile app exploitation. Main impacts are on *availability* (operations / settlement) and *integrity* (billing/configuration). Because CSMS acts as a central coordinator, several threats attract $k = 1.2$, reflecting the potential to remotely affect an entire fleet of stations. As a result, even moderate-severity exploits can escalate to

High when systemic effects are factored in. However, certain misconfigurations (e.g., weak rate limiting or isolated server leaks) are kept at $k = 1.0$ because they degrade only the directly affected instance without credible fleet-wide consequences, remaining in the Low–Moderate range. Thus, the CSMS domain underscores how centralization amplifies risk: central APIs and authentication issues must be secured to prevent cascading service-wide outages.

Electrical grid infrastructure. Direct EV–electrical grid coupling is limited, but when it occurs, impacts can be severe: grid overloads, substation sabotage, or manipulation of protection systems. Safety scores are high ($H = 4–5$), and systemic cascading is plausible across feeders, hence $k = 1.2$. Accordingly, Critical risks are observed (e.g., V2G overload, substation breaker tampering). Still, likelihood values for such advanced attacks are low ($L = 2–3$), due to required expertise, resources, and access. This dampens the aggregate risk, explaining why some threats fall in the Medium–High range even with severe impacts. Grid risks, therefore, appear as “low frequency, high consequence” events—rare but catastrophic if realized—demanding resilience investments despite their lower probability.

Utility control systems. Insider misuse, privilege abuse, and weak segmentation are the main concerns. All threats are systemic: a compromise of SCADA or operator consoles can spread across grid operations. For this reason, $k = 1.2$ is applied to all cases. Despite the fact that likelihood is relatively low, the safety impact is high ($H = 5$). Together with the systemic propagation, every UCS threat is included in the *Critical* range. UCS stands out as the highest-risk domain in the ecosystem, with no Low or Moderate entries. This underscores the need to secure operator consoles, enforce strict segmentation, and strengthen insider access controls.

Cloud & storage systems. Threats include credential theft and server misconfiguration, which affect user data *confidentiality* and *integrity*. The impact on human safety is minimal ($H = 1$). Cloud providers are considered resilient, which means that availability issues are limited. Most cases remain at $k = 1.0$. This happens because effects like leaked credentials or exposed logs can not be spread to other systems. Overall, risk is calculated in the *Low–Moderate* range levels. A misconfigured server which only leads to credential dumping, for example, scores *Low*, since it has no safety impact. It does not have cascading failures, either. And mainly it is usually fixed quickly by providers. In short, cloud risks are relevant but are not considered safety-critical. Thus, they can be managed effectively.

Battery storage systems. Manipulated charging cycles or corrupted BMS telemetry can harm battery life and safety ($H = 4–5$). These lead to *High* or *Critical* risks, especially when overcharging may cause thermal runaway or fire. Spread is limited ($k = 1.0–1.1$), as even if one unit is affected, the impact rarely goes beyond that site. Nevertheless, the safety implications mean no BSS threat is Low. They are all at least *Medium*. This shows that in BSS, even a local compromise brings real hazards, highlighting the need for built-in safeguards against tampered control logic.

On-site energy systems. Threats include FDI, disabling PV panels, and local DoS attacks. Most cases fall under *Moderate risk* because they have a limited safety impact ($H = 2–3$) and minimal spread ($k = 1.0–1.1$). For example, turning off panels or sending incorrect generation data is mainly related to billing issues or local availability, and not safety-critical systems. Low-impact incidents, such as power theft or disabling one panel, remain at the *Low risk* level, as their effects are financial or isolated, without resulting in wider failures. Overall, OES risks are considered rather contained, in comparison to other sectors. Nevertheless, they still play an important role for economic stability and operator confidence.

Discussion. The comprehensive system-level threat analysis of this section demonstrates that a large proportion of the identified attack vectors are classified as Critical or High risk. These include unauthorized firmware modification, insecure update mechanisms, malware injection, privilege escalation, data manipulation, and communication-layer exploits. Not only such risks are technically advanced, they can also undermine the integrity and reliability of connected EV systems. As a result, even a minor issue may quickly escalate and affect the entire network.

Typical security measures remain necessary. For example, code signing is normally used for software authenticity verification. Network segmentation makes it more difficult for cyber-attackers to move deeper into a system. MFA provides stronger protection for account holders. However, these solutions rely on centralized trust. If a central authority is compromised, the overall security chain is threatened. Moreover, since auditing strongly depends on log files (which maybe altered or deleted by skilled cyber-attackers), verifying what has really happened can become challenging.

This gap highlights where blockchain technologies can serve as a complementary layer of protection. At the most general level, blockchain introduces three properties that are highly relevant to the threats identified: decentralization, immutability, and transparency. Decentralization reduces dependence on any single trusted authority, limiting the impact of insider threats or compromised nodes. Immutability ensures that once events are recorded, they cannot be altered or erased, thereby providing reliable evidence of system activity. Transparency, when applied in a controlled manner, enables all relevant stakeholders - manufacturers, operators, regulators, and even end users-to share a consistent and verifiable view of critical events.

When considering firmware-related threats, the risks of unauthorized modification or insecure updates reflect the need for stronger guarantees of provenance and integrity. Blockchain supports this requirement by providing a trustworthy record of update events, ensuring that any attempt to introduce unverified firmware can be detected and rejected. In the case of malware injection or privilege escalation, the central issue lies in weak or mismanaged identity and access control. Here, blockchain contributes by reinforcing accountability: access rights and privilege use can be monitored in a tamper-resistant manner, which makes misuse both more difficult and more visible.

Communication-layer attacks, including replay and MiTM manipulation, demonstrate the risks that arise when distributed nodes lack reliable mechanisms to validate message authenticity. Blockchain directly addresses these challenges by ensuring that once a transaction or exchange is validated, it cannot be replayed or silently altered, thereby neutralizing common avenues for data manipulation. Similarly, in electrical grid and SCADA domains, where protocol manipulation and data injection can cause cascading failures, blockchain enables distributed validation of control commands and telemetry, reducing the ability of a single compromised actor to disrupt operations.

BSS represents another domain of heightened concern, as malicious data injection or manipulated charging cycles can affect both system performance and physical safety. Here, blockchain supports greater operational resilience by ensuring that key events - such as charging instructions and telemetry -are logged in a tamper-evident manner and can be independently verified by multiple actors. This reduces opportunities for manipulation to remain undetected, while also providing a stronger foundation for accountability.

Taken together, these findings suggest that the most severe risks across the EV ecosystem are those where integrity, authenticity, and accountability are most at stake. By aligning directly with these dimensions, blockchain provides a structural enhancement to the defensive posture of EV infrastructures. It does not replace conventional controls but complements them, addressing precisely those areas where residual risks persist. In doing so, blockchain reinforces trust in the broader ecosystem and reduces the likelihood that localized compromises escalate into systemic failures.

4. Blockchain technology application to EV infrastructure services

Due to the latest malicious exploitations threatening EV's security, blockchain technology has been extensively applied to EV charging processes. Blockchain has offered an unparalleled technology and a viable solution for augmenting energy transactions with utmost protection by processing transactions from various nodes within the system, which are then collected into blocks and disseminated across the network. The blocks are securely linked together and sealed via cryptographic hashes, thus diminishing the risks of malicious or unauthorized activities in an EV infrastructure that can be prevented via blockchain's immutability.

In the following part, recent literature work (i.e., 35 total frameworks) is analyzed for the deployment of blockchain technologies in the most common EV services (presented in Section 2). A summary of the analyzed frameworks along with the employed blockchain mechanisms (i.e., platform, consensus protocol, architectural blockchain elements, and threat prevention techniques) is then provided in Table 7 and mapped according to the EV services where they are applicable to.

4.1. EV charging process

The communication within traditional EVCS introduces challenges in terms of security, interoperability, privacy, and trust. Conventional payment processes for EV charging usually involve various intermediaries, leading to complicated and time-consuming transactions. Security and transparency are critical in the EV charging domain during the verification of the EVCS' authenticity [262].

4.1.1. Consensus security

As a significant part of blockchain technology, the consensus protocol's security and performance primarily define the efficiency of a blockchain-enabled network [263]. In the EV charging scenario, where the number of EVs and EVCSs participating in the charging process is considerable, the conventional consensus protocols, such as PoW, are challenging to meet the scalable and efficient requirements necessitated for enormous amounts of EV charging data. Therefore, it is essential to design specific consensus algorithms for such scenarios.

Comprehending the significance of consensus for addressing security issues regarding data integrity and billing charging processes, the work of Su et al. [242] proposed a blockchain-enabled EV charging framework that uses the DBFT consensus algorithm based on the reputation of the consensus nodes for securing charging services within the permissioned blockchain setting. Similarly, for addressing the issue of manipulating the charging process that leads to energy theft, the authors of [243] proposed a proof-of-concept framework for transparency and automation on the billing process based on a permissioned and private blockchain platform. Qian et al. [246] used PBFT and a distributed auction-based protocol to address the manipulation of charging records and possible generated overhead due to operational cost.

4.1.2. Smart contracts

Blockchain-enabled smart contracts offer the potential of a secured charging process by validating user credentials, vehicle identity, and payment information, enforcing energy metering and secure billing to automate and facilitate transaction regulations [247]. Solidity-based smart contracts and mutual authentication is used in Kim et al. [248], to govern the charging process, achieve perfect forward secrecy, and address replay, impersonation, session key disclosure, and MiTM attacks. Smart contracts and a reputation-based DBFT consensus protocol are proposed in [249], for secure EV charging against Sybil and whitewashing attacks. With the smart contracts to receive inputs from both the buyer's and the seller's smart meters to prevent malicious buyers or sellers from submitting fraudulent charging services, this framework validates the amount of energy consumed and spent, respectively.

Reward-based smart contracts for a blockchain-enabled EV charging framework are proposed in Lee et al. [251], where the reward is based on the history of a contribution value of each charging station. Evaluated with Hyperledger Fabric and the Raft consensus protocol, this framework focuses on establishing secure charging data-sharing and resilience against false information propagation, impersonation, and collusion attacks. Huang et al. [253] used smart contracts and the Bitcoin-based lightning network to address key-related attacks that occur during the registration, authentication, and scheduling phases for EV charging management. Similarly, authentication attacks are addressed via Ethereum-based smart contracts in [254]. Key-related attacks are also addressed in Saha et al. [255], in which Hyperledger Fabric with PBFT and smart contracts are implemented alongside signcryption and *Hierarchical Key Generation* (HKG) for cryptographic keys based on lattice constructions to secure the EV charging ecosystem.

4.1.3. Blockchain privacy

Frequent scheduling of EV charging might raise privacy concerns, exposing the EV user's charging pattern to service providers [245]. Analyzing the EV owner's geographical location, attackers can obtain the owner's home address, location, and workplace.

Consortium and private blockchains are commonly used to address privacy issues encountered in EV charging systems. The authors of [245] used fog computing, a Proof of online Duration (PoD) consensus protocol, a mutual authentication protocol, and a consortium blockchain for securing the communication among EV components, while the privacy of EV owners is secured against privacy leakage attacks. Similarly, the authors of [244] proposed a privacy-preserving authentication framework with ZKPs and blockchain technology to ensure the EV owner's authentication and anonymity, but also to secure the EV charging infrastructure against MiTM, DoS, and replay attacks. Lin et al. [250] proposed an Ethereum-based and AI-enhanced CSMS, in which smart contracts and a lightweight Proof-of-Work (LWPOW) consensus protocol preserve user anonymity and prevent data leaking attacks. To preserve anonymity, address impersonation and other privacy-related attacks, the works of [241] and [252] proposed a privacy-preserving blockchain-enabled framework based on Hyperledger Fabric and smart contracts.

4.2. Energy trading services

In conventional and rapidly evolving EV-oriented energy trading systems, the stakeholders apply insecure communication and computational methods for preserving and processing the related information, with the energy trading applications depending upon the data regarding the available EV's charge capacity to determine whether the designated and nearby charging station is suitable or trustworthy [264]. In addition, the EV owners necessitate the energy trading-related information to be visible, accurate, and trusted for ensuring secure operations during EV-oriented energy trading, without any privacy violations [265].

Meanwhile, the large growth of EVs generates several thousand energy trading transactions that need to be collected, preserved, and processed. In such scenarios, high latency cannot be tolerated, and therefore fast and real-time processing of energy transactions is necessary [266]. To counter such risks, several incentive mechanisms based on monetary and trust have been proposed to secure services on EV-oriented energy trading. However, monetary approaches rely on centralized servers, which are vulnerable to single points of failure, while trust mechanisms are susceptible to insider attacks, such as Sybil and whitewashing [262].

Blockchain technology is acknowledged as a promising solution for addressing security risks commonly imposed on traditional EV-oriented energy trading systems. Data immutability and transparency enhance the energy transactions' visibility and the detection of fraudulent activities, while the energy traders can access and verify the comprehensive historical data regarding the energy trading process [264]. This integration eliminates middle parties via decentralization and averts security

Table 7
Blockchain-enabled frameworks for EV security.

Service	Framework	Platform	Consensus	Architectural Blockchain Elements	Threat Prevention
Energy Trading	[227]	Fabric	BAC-SDS	Byzantine consensus	Sybil, double spending and energy attacks
	[228]	Fabric	PBFT	Game theory & Reputation-based consensus	Double spending, Sybil and 51% attacks
	[229]	N/A	BFT	Byzantine consensus	Data tampering, false data injection attacks, manipulation in the SCADA information
	[230]	N/A	RBCET	Reputation-based consensus	Sybil, double spending, DoS, eclipse, and collusion attacks.
	[231]	Sim.	DPOSP	Byzantine consensus, fog computing	Privacy leakage, tampering and bifurcation attacks
	[232]	Fabric	BAC	Reputation-based consensus	Sybil, DoS and data tampering
	[233]	Ethereum	PoA	Smart contracts, incentive mechanisms	Double spending and sybil attack
	[234]	Ethereum	PoW	Smart contracts, IPFS	Data linkage attacks, denial of payment, and privacy disclosure
	[235]	Ethereum	PoW	Smart contracts	Data tampering, trust issues among EVCSs and EVs
	[236]	Ethereum	POA	Smart contracts, auction mechanism	Data tampering
	[237]	Fabric	PBFT	Incentive-based smart contracts, Game Theory	Collusion, MitM, spoofing and tampering attacks
	[238]	Kovan(Ethereum)	PoA	ZKP, smart contracts	Sybil, MiTM, DoS and collusion attacks
	[239]	Sim ^a .	PBFT	Mutual authentication, Byzantine consensus	Replay, MiTM, secret leakage, hijacking, DoS attacks
	[240]	Fabric	N/A	N/A	Charge and payment tampering, privacy disclosure, fraudulent trading
	[241]	Fabric	N/A	ZKPs, smart contracts	Privacy leakage
EV Charging	[242]	N/A	DBFT	Reputation-based consensus, smart contracts	Malicious energy provider (fraudulent charging services), malicious TTP
	[243]	Fabric	Kafka	Private and permissioned blockchain	Fraudulent CSP
	[244]	Ethereum	PoW	ZKPs	EVSP, MitM, DoS, Replay attacks
	[245]	Fabric	PoD	Authentication and mutual authorisation, fog computing	Sybil, impersonation, privacy leakage and DoS attacks
	[246]	Sim	PBFT	Byzantine consensus, auction-based algorithm	Data manipulation
	[247]	Fabric	PBFT	Byzantine consensus, smart contracts	MiTM, DoS, malware and false data injection attacks
	[248]	Ethereum	N/A	Smart contracts, mutual authentication	Replay, impersonation, session key disclosure and MiTM attacks
	[249]	N/A	DBFT	Smart contracts, Reputation-based and Byzantine consensus	Sybil and whitewashing attacks
	[250]	Ethereum	LWPoW	AI	Anonymity and data leaking attacks
	[251]	Fabric	Raft	Reward-based smart contracts	False information propagation, impersonation and collusion attacks
	[252]	Fabric	Raft	Mixing techniques, group signatures	Impersonation and privacy-related attacks
	[253]	Bitcoin	Lightning	Smart contracts	Key-related attacks
	[254]	Ethereum	N/A	Smart contracts	Key-related attacks
	[255]	Fabric	PBFT	Smart contracts, lattices	Key-related, data tampering and injection attacks
	Energy management	[256]	Sim.	Sim.	Optimization algorithm
[257]		Sim.	Sim.	Smart contracts, incentive mechanisms	Data tampering
[258]		Fabric	Kafka	Smart contracts	MITM attacks, DoS attacks and injection attacks
[259]		Fabric	PoD	Privacy-preserving authentication protocol	Replay, impersonation, MiTM and privacy related attacks
[260]		Private	DAGs	Consensus security, Stochastic scheme	Data tampering attacks
[261]		Sim.	PoLH	MFA and matrix-based authentication	Authentication-based and data tampering attacks

^a Simulated environments.

threats as well as malicious activities stemming from centralized service providers. With anonymous and secure interactions among users and with the transactional data of EV-oriented energy trading to be preserved in an immutable and distributed ledger, resilience against cyber-attacks can be achieved [267].

4.2.1. Consensus security

Consensus protocols offer an additional layer of security in blockchain-enabled EV-oriented energy trading systems. Since consensus is considered a significant module when blockchain technology is applied to energy trading [227], it can be used to prevent double claims of payment and to penalize malicious trading transactions via reputation-based mechanisms [228]. However, the latency that can occur during the consensus process can lead to major delays in the operation of the energy trading transactions [266]. Therefore, efficient

consensus algorithms are required to execute transactions in a secure and time-efficient manner to satisfy the requirements of energy trading applications.

Towards addressing attacks on energy trading processes, various frameworks have been proposed. Sheikh et al. [229] integrated a Byzantine fault-tolerant approach with an offloading scheme to avert possible manipulation of the SCADA information, but also to address data tampering, false data injection, and other attacks that can occur on sensor data, on communication links, and on actuators. Realizing the importance of consensus within Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) energy trading systems, Wang et al. [227] used Hyperledger Fabric with a customized consensus algorithm, BAC-SDS, which is based on Hashgraph, and it is enabled with asynchronous BFT properties for addressing Sybil, double spending, and energy attacks, as well as for maximizing the use of renewable energy.

Abishu et al. [228] integrated a PBFT-based consensus with a trust management model and a two-stage Stackelberg game to motivate, via rewards, energy sellers involved in energy trading, addressing thus double spending, Sybil, and 51% attacks. Similarly, double-spending, eclipse, DDoS, Sybil, and collusion attacks are addressed in [230] via a Reputation-Based Consensus Protocol for Energy Trading (RBCET), in which the reputation scores of EVs and EVCS are computed based on a decision tree regressor model. This work enables only the nodes whose reputation score is above a certain threshold to participate in energy trading activities.

Fog computing is used in [231] along with a novel consensus protocol, called DPOSP, that is based on PBFT and DPOS, for addressing privacy leakage, tampering, and bifurcation attacks. A Direct Acyclic Graph (DAG), and more specifically a Hashgraph-based protocol, called “*Block Alliance Consensus*” (BAC), is integrated with Hyperledger Fabric in [232]. Based on the randomness of a leader election model, this work proposes to prevent V2V systems from Sybil, DDoS, and data tampering attacks in large-scale networks.

4.2.2. Smart contracts

Blockchain technology also empowers self-executable programs, the smart contracts, to define the rules that have been acknowledged by all the participating entities in the blockchain network. In EV-oriented energy trading systems, the blockchain smart contracts can be triggered, if certain conditions are met, to regulate energy trading events, as well as to facilitate automated and secure trading activities among participating entities. Triggered events and predefined energy-sharing states are some of the functionalities that can be offered from the execution of blockchain-based smart contracts within an untrusted energy market.

Leveraging the technology of blockchain smart contracts, Khalid et al. [233] proposed an EV-oriented energy trading system for automated, efficient, and secure energy trading. The proposed framework is deployed with Ethereum using a PoA consensus protocol, while the smart contracts, along with an incentive mechanism, are designed to address double-spending and sybil attacks, but also to verify fair payment among EVs, thus encouraging participation in energy trading.

Sadiq et al. [234] utilized smart contracts, the Interplanetary File-System (IPFS), the Ethereum blockchain platform, and a PoW-based consensus protocol to tackle security and privacy issues related to data linkage, privacy disclosure, and denial of payment attacks. The smart contracts are designed for autonomous trading activities, tackling trading disputes, while IPFS is deployed for ensuring constant access and reliable preservation of the traded energy data. Asfia et al. [235] proposed a smart contract-enabled blockchain network for addressing data tampering and trust issues that can occur during energy trading between EVCS and EVs.

Taking into account the uncertainty of EVs’ charging and discharging process that can occur from data tampering attacks, Liu et al. [236] developed automated contracts running on Ethereum and a reverse auction mechanism, in which a dynamic pricing strategy is used to fulfill the transaction matching. Chen et al. [237] used smart contracts with game theory to incentivize the participation of EVs in energy trading scenarios with Hyperledger Fabric, PBFT, and incentive-based smart contracts to achieve unforgeability and address collusion, MitM, and tampering attacks.

4.2.3. Blockchain privacy

The adoption of blockchain technology has efficiently addressed privacy concerns with privacy preservation mechanisms, such as pseudonymisation, mixing, and homomorphic encryption techniques, as well as Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP), to be integrated within the blockchain platform. Therefore, EV-oriented energy trading can be conducted in a privacy-preserving manner, with the EV owners’ sensitive information remaining secure.

To address privacy-oriented challenges, Baza et al. [238] proposed a Charging-Station-to-Vehicle (CS2V) energy trading framework. The

proposed solution, built on top of the Kovan blockchain platform, uses anonymization to address collusion, MitM, and Sybil attacks with a common-prefix linkable anonymous authentication scheme based on zk-SNARKs. Sharma et al. [239] proposed sTrade, an energy trading system for secure and privacy-preserving V2G mutual authentication network using lightweight elliptic curve cryptography to address MiTM, secret leakage, hijacking, and DoS attacks. The blockchain solution is based on PBFT, evaluated using the AVISPA simulation tool, and a novel EVCS scheduling protocol is proposed to reduce the charging and discharging waiting times. Zhu et al. [240] proposed a framework for V2G networks, in which payment auditing and data privacy are achieved via the integrated privacy-preserving techniques of Hyperledger Fabric.

4.3. Energy management services

With the substitution of conventional vehicles with EVs, energy preservation systems are expected to serve as the backbone for enabling urban e-mobility [259]. However, cyber-attacks targeting Lithium-ion (Li-ion) BMS pose new risks via the security vulnerabilities of traditional hardware and software architectures. More precisely, by manipulating battery algorithms, sensing data, and control commands, the attackers can overheat batteries, leading to fire incidents on EVs or even battery explosions [268]. An awareness of such important security challenges from malicious attackers will progress further.

Integrating blockchain technology into EV-BMS can improve energy efficiency and sustainability of electric mobility by tracking the life-cycle of batteries and energy exchanges. Via a decentralised process of constant tracking battery records, such as impedance spectroscopy, cell chemistry, and voltage, better control over the EV batteries’ life-cycle can be accomplished, starting from the manufacturing process to recycling or even to second usage [261]. Chinnaperumal et al. [261] used *Multi-Factor Authentication* (MFA) and matrix-based authentication along with the *Proof of Lightweight Hash* (PoLH) consensus protocol, which combines PoW and PoA, for prioritizing performance and governance in battery preservation systems and EVs to enable only authorized participants in the transactions’ validation. Kim et al. [258] used Hyperledger Fabric and smart contracts for comprehensive battery monitoring against security vulnerabilities of BMSs.

While EVs assist in environmental sustainability [269], several challenges regarding the EV charging wait-times are encountered [270]. For this reason, battery-swapping technology emerges as a viable solution for replacing EV charging points. However, additional privacy and data security concerns have been added with this solution for EV owners. To address such issues, privacy-preserving authentication protocols based on blockchain technology can verify the security and the credibility of data preservation processes. Chen et al. [259] proposed a privacy-preserving blockchain-enabled framework with Hyperledger Fabric in conjunction with a Proof-of-Data (PoD) consensus protocol for battery swapping. In particular, the authors proposed a mutual authentication protocol founded on an intelligent blockchain mechanism for efficiently managing and safekeeping battery exchange records against replay, MiTM, impersonation, and privacy-related attacks.

5. Proposed blockchain-enabled EV architecture

Considering the information presented in Section 4 and specifically in Table 7, a main summary is that the selection of a blockchain platform for addressing cyber-attacks in the EV infrastructure should incorporate a multitude of criteria.

Initially, most of the frameworks presented that the integration of a permissioned blockchain platform, such as Hyperledger Fabric, results in a secure system with a transparent audit trail for addressing the security issues occurring in an EV ecosystem. EV charging, energy trading, and energy management necessitate robust security guarantees regarding accountability, access control, and deterministic finality. Taking into

Fig. 2. A high-level overview of the proposed architecture.

account this consideration, this section presents a layered Zero-Trust framework for distributed energy trading, retail EV charging, and grid-enabled energy management - and purposefully integrates blockchain technology, distributed file-sharing with content addressing, multiparty application bus, remote attestation processes, and structured observability. Illustrated in Fig. 2, the proposed unified framework is partitioned into three different layers, due to the diverse attack surfaces and trust assumptions usually encountered in EV ecosystems.

5.1. The three-layered architecture

The **physical layer** is comprised of the devices that produce primary measurements and interoperate with the electrical infrastructure. Prevaling components include EVs equipped with bidirectional chargers and built-in metering; stationary EVCS (AC or DC) featuring embedded OCPP communication standards; DER control gateways with *Behind-the-Meter* (BTM) storage and PV integration; roadside wireless and dynamic power transfer modules, substation and feeder meters; and actuators that are responsible for transforming electrical signals, received from the control system, to physical activities. Then, an assumption is made that each of these devices is treated as compromised, unless integrity is verified.

Integrity is verified by remote attestation processes, with each device hosting a remote attestation agent. Leveraging TPM-based attestation measurements to attest runtime integrity constantly, the attestation agent is bound to a measurement policy. This policy contains digitally signed and verifiable binaries, permissible firmware hashes, and a list of processes and container images capable to interact with the actuators and the sensors. In the physical layer, all the communications between devices are mutually authenticated over TLS and hardware-anchored certificates signed only when effective remote attestation is conducted. Metering records and control messages are distinctly signed, carrying counters and nonce values, associated with a session-specific timing to avert replay attacks.

Local Aggregators (LAGs) placed on micro-grids, utility cabinets, and depots are used for transaction management, for receiving charging requests from adjacent EVs, and for ephemerally preserving incoming telemetry information. LAGs are supplied with wireless interfaces and energy distribution centers within the allocated region, offering services at both EVCSs and EVs as wireless communication and local energy distribution [262].

The **cloud layer** delivers services that occur from mutual authentication between organizations. The blockchain network, which is built on top of Hyperledger Fabric, offers a private and permissioned blockchain platform with four private channels. Each channel is used for ad-

addressing different EV security concerns, with the trading channel to be deployed for auctions and *Private Power Purchase Agreements* (PPAs); the EV charging channel for consumer sessions; the EMS channel for energy-adjustment requests and confirmations; and the auditing channel for tamper-resistant evidence from system logs. Consensus on the transactions' total order is established only when the endorsement policies are fulfilled, requiring thus signatures from different stakeholders, such as the electrical grid operator and the CPO, prior to the approval of each energy transaction.

Robustness and efficiency are achieved via preservation of high-volume data artifacts in the private IPFS file-sharing system, where the artifacts are encrypted with the corresponding integrity hashes and *Content Identifiers* (CIDs) to be preserved on the distributed ledger, offering thus immutability and verifiable integrity without on-chain preservation cost [271]. Hyperledger Firefly acts not only as an API wrapper, but also as the coordinator, the data bus, and the orchestrator of the proposed blockchain-enabled system conducting multi-party operations. Sequencing off-chain file distribution, communications, and on-chain interactions, Hyperledger Firefly handles mTLS offloading, OAuth token verification, *distributed identities* (DIDs), certificate pinning, and web-application fire-walling, among others [272].

In the EV charging scenario, with the initiation of a charging session, Hyperledger Firefly organizes the documentation of meter values, the payment escrow, and the initiation of the preservation to the distributed ledger. In the trading scenario, Hyperledger Firefly acts as the broker for bid commitments sequencing and revealing the results. The identity of each device or service, in the cloud, is associated with the blockchain's private and permissioned nature, along with Keylime's cloud registrar and verifier [273], where short-time-lived certificates to limit the effect of secret leakage are acquired after the fulfillment of the policies in the attestation process.

The Fabric's membership service provider generates enrollment certificates that exclusively rely upon the attestation evidence. Each EVCS obtains anonymous credentials via Hyperledger Fabric's identity mixer (Idemix),³ while DIDs and verifiable credentials (VCs) are managed by Hyperledger Firefly. Re-issuance of certificates for extending access is conditioned on the provision of fresh attestation evidence. Therefore, the design of requiring clean attestation results and membership verifications in the private channel with ephemeral credentials is well aligned with the Zero-Trust security principle of "never trust, always verify".

The application layer establishes the business and service tier of the unified framework for EV ecosystems. Constituted from dashboards, operator portals, market engines, and end-user applications that conduct trading matching, auctions, and energy management orchestration, the application layer offers case management and dispute resolution, operations console, security monitoring, and establishes device data gathering for analysis. Operational control is expressed via transactions that publish events on the distributed ledger, such as energy management intents (approval or refusal), new sessions (initiated or stopped), or expelled misbehaving identities. Security monitoring, provided with structured logs collected from Fluent Bit, offers alerting for unusual behavior, such as irregular session patterns or bidding, failed attestations, and unauthorized activities. Case-management and disputes' resolution is offered via transactions' identifiers and the corresponding CIDs from IPFS, while unmasking is provided, for revealing a participant's identity, when appropriate conditions are met.

5.2. Application scenarios for EV services

The proposed architecture is hereby applied to the most common EV services that were presented in Section 2. Initially, in the EV charging scenario of Fig. 3, secure onboarding of EV components is established via remote attestation services. The deployed agents submit runtime mea-

Fig. 3. Blockchain integration scenario in the EV charging service.

surements and TPM-based boot values to the cloud verifier, over mTLS, anchored to certificates. Then, the verifier compares the received results with predefined and clean state values that include metrology binaries, container hashes, and approved kernel images [271]. Upon successful results, the registrar generates a short-lived credential with the organization's CA to issue a Fabric onboarding certificate. Subsequent thereto, the Idemix issuer supplies the device with anonymous credentials to enable market participation in a privacy-preserving manner, with the right to receive credentials to be dependent upon unique hardware.

5.2.1. The EV charging scenario for EV services

Upon each EV's connection to an EVCS, mutual authentication is performed and a new ephemeral ticket is generated as proof of recent verification of the EVCS's integrity, which is included in each start-session message. The EV charging smart contract initiates a pre-financed escrow, with the payment to be delivered automatically upon the verification of the delivered energy. The meter measurements, signed by the EVCS, retain increasing counters that are sent to the LAG for preservation in IPFS. With the session's termination, the escrow delivers the payment when the meter values are valid, or initiates a dispute on the distributed ledger referencing the evidentiary data preserved on IPFS. This process is illustrated in Figure 3 and can be used to address security attacks targeting the EV charging scenario; DoS attacks during charging rush hours are addressed via LAGs to rate-limit devices; denial of payment and tampering of charging meter values are handled via on-chain dispute resolution with verifiable evidence, while MitM and replay attacks via timestamps and increasing counters.

5.2.2. The EV trading scenario for EV services

In the EV trading scenario, presented in Fig. 4, energy purchasers and prosumers participate in auctions with anonymous credentials that prove membership without revealing their identities. In an auction's opening, the prosumer submits, via Firefly and within a designated time window, a hashed bid transaction on the blockchain. This transaction contains the bid, i.e., the quantity, its price, and a random nonce value, without including the plain-text bid.

Right afterwards, a stake-bond is transferred from the prosumer to the escrow service as punishment of possible malicious behavior, which will result in bond forfeiture [274]. The same procedure is performed from the buyer's side as well, with these commitments to be stored,

³ <https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/latest/idemix.html>

Fig. 4. Blockchain integration scenario in the energy trading service.

Fig. 5. Blockchain integration scenario in the energy management service.

sequentially, on the distributed ledger. In the reveal phase, where the auction window is closed, each party submits a transaction revealing the plain-text of the bid, which is compared against the commitment. Unrevealed or mismatching commitments are automatically excluded, resulting in stake forfeiture. With the revealed commitments to be matched, physical delivery is then followed by signed energy measurements to be stored on IPFS and the corresponding CIDs and hashes on the distributed ledger.

In case of inconsistent values on the consumed and sold energy, a dispute case is initiated by the escrow service for settlement, pointing to the corresponding CIDs in IPFS. With regulators to supervise the energy market for ensuring compliance with the corresponding energy policies, secure and fair trading procedures are cultivated. In particular, data linkage attacks are addressed by anonymizing energy buyers and sellers, with a fresh pseudonym to be used in each new bid; collusion and front-running attacks via consensus sequencing of transactions, while disputes are resolved, via the regulator, by revealing identities and by pointing to the signed measurements preserved in IPFS.

5.2.3. The EV-EMS scenario for EV services

In the EV-EMS scenario, presented in Fig. 5, the physical layer devices, such as EV-BMSS, EVCS, PV inverters, and feeder meters, host TPM agents, which attest boot measurements and runtime. Each device

is considered untrusted until a fresh proof-of-integrity is presented to allow short-lived and renewed credentials to be issued after policy compliance. Any possible deviation from the policies follows automatic termination of the mutually authenticated sessions.

The EMS submits intents, which are signed, time-bounded envelopes that define permissibility across a time window for a specific set of assets; for EVs and EVCSs encode the power limit, the power's rate of change, the V2G eligibility, and the (minimum) state of charge; for PVs encode the limitations and the rate on power, the power's ramps and the references concerning to watt/VAR or volt/VAR profiles; and for BESSs encode the state of charge, the depth of charge/discharge and c-rate thresholds.

The intents that will be sent via Hyperledger Firefly are securely stored in IPFS. Meanwhile, the corresponding CIDs, along with the proofs of energy delivery, are preserved in Hyperledger Fabric's EMS channel. EVCS periodically queries the stored intents via Hyperledger Firefly, and prior to the intents' acceptance, they verify the attestation results. If attestation fails, then a signed refusal, which references the rule that thwarted compliance, is sent to the blockchain network. Impersonation and hijacking attacks are addressed with constant and renewed attestations, while false-data injection and MiTM attacks are addressed within signed and bounded time frames.

5.2.4. Blockchain attack surface and mitigation

While the architecture is proposed to enhance integrity and accountability, it also addresses EV-centric cyber-attacks. Specifically, blockchain technology itself, when implemented in critical EV infrastructures, introduces a new attack surface. Consensus attacks, in the ordering service, can cause message reordering, DoS in the transactions' processing, and collisions between orderers, allowing adversaries to launch front-running attacks by leveraging early bid-content disclosure before the reveal phase of the auction process. Such attacks, in the proposed architecture, are mitigated with fault-tolerant consensus protocols, such as RAFT or Smart-BFT, which enforce strong leader election and can detect malicious behavior.

Additionally, a compromised CA can issue new certificates, allowing malicious clients to submit transactions with falsified meter values or even to obtain authorized access to private or sensitive data. However, new certificates can be reissued only upon fresh remote attestation with new attestation measurements and clean attestation evidence. Nevertheless, data linkage and privacy disclosure are issues commonly encountered when blockchain technology is integrated with EV architectures [234]. Private channels that bind operations to roles and specify chaincode function invocations, and a private network of IPFS, enforce explicit access control policies.

6. Proof-of-concept blockchain framework evaluation

In this section, we provide a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed blockchain framework with experiments carried out on an emulated testbed. Specifically, the testbed allows the implementation of the blockchain-enabled architecture for the EV-oriented services and has been recently introduced for the EV charging service on [5]. Initially, we present the EV charging testbed setup, and then we focus on describing the blockchain platform's evaluation results under a load testing approach.

6.1. EV charging testbed setup

The EV charging testbed setup that is used is based on both AC and DC chargers, configured in the SAP e-mobility environment⁴ and further explained in [5]). Even though SAP is used as an emulation environment in this testbed, it has also been validated against actual EVCS of existing

⁴ <https://github.com/sap/e-mobility-charging-stations-simulator>

Fig. 6. An overview of the experimental testbed for EV charging security evaluation and blockchain mitigation of cyber-attacks.

CPOs, hence providing the required testbed validity with respect to real EV charging conditions. Furthermore, the EVCS are transmitting energy consumption measurements (i.e., Current, Voltage, Active and Reactive Power) through OCPP to the CSMS system, which, based on the protocol, are called *Meter Values*. Moreover, the CSMS in the testbed is based on the Steve CSMS⁵.

For the conducted evaluation, we have setup three KEBA AC and one ABB DC EVCS configured with 30 second transmission window for *Meter Values* in EV charging sessions, emulating sessions with a total duration of 125 hours (i.e., 5 days and 5 hours). The emulated environment was executed for 12 minutes, and the *Meter Values* are received from the CSMS system. Furthermore, upon the reception of the *StopTransaction* message, the CSMS platform calculates the overall energy consumed in the EV charging session.

Upon the deployment of the EV charging setup, we have conducted FDI and Denial of Charge (DoC) attack scenarios, which are also described as data tampering and DDoS, respectively, in Section 3. Both scenarios were executed on the testbed and were based on initial access obtained by exploiting vulnerabilities of the wireless infrastructure (i.e., router) and then followed by a MiTM attack between the EVCS and CSMS systems that are illustrated in Fig. 6a. The two attack scenarios, even though they include the same initial steps, differ in terms of goals. Specifically, the goal of the FDI attack is to falsify the values during the EV charging session as well as when the session has finished, whereas the DoC attack focuses on blocking a legitimate EV charging session from ever being started, by making the EVCS unresponsive (i.e., converting the OCPP *StartTransaction* to a *Reset* message).

6.2. Blockchain framework evaluation experiments

Having the EV charging testbed as the reference scenario, the architecture of the framework is built and depicted in Fig. 6b. Specifically, when an energy consumption measurement is generated, it is sent to the blockchain application (Hyperledger Firefly, Fabric, and IPFS) to be

Fig. 7. Average electrical power (falsified and with blockchain) over the number of the energy transactions. The blue line illustrates the original meter values preserved on the proposed blockchain framework and the red line illustrates the meter values under the FDI attack.

preserved as a blockchain transaction. With the preservation of the meter measurement in IPFS, via Hyperledger Firefly, the blockchain transaction is submitted for execution to the blockchain peers (endorsers), which endorse the transaction's signature and confirm the operation's authorization. In our case, we preserve energy consumption measurements (i.e., the *Meter Values*), during 1) the EV charging session and 2) upon the *StopTransaction* to stop the active session (i.e., *meterStop*). Such values allow for testing the blockchain application's performance and address FDI and DoC attacks against EV services.

With the execution phase to be completed, the transaction is sent to the ordering service. The ordering service achieves consensus regarding the transactions' total order and creates new blocks using the Raft consensus protocol⁶. Upon establishing consensus, the newly created block is sent to the validating peers. Before appending the block to the distributed ledger, the validating peers confirm that each transaction's payload is still accurate and that no modifications have been performed to the blockchain since each transaction's execution.

⁵ <https://github.com/steve-community/steve>

⁶ https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/latest/raft_configuration.html

Fig. 8. Performance results of the proposed blockchain-enabled EV charging framework in the load testing approach.

For evaluating the performance of the proposed blockchain-enabled EV charging infrastructure, the *Meter Values* created from the EVCS delivered the perfect scenario for performing a load testing approach in the blockchain application and are depicted in Fig. 7 alongside the falsified *Meter Values* from the FDI attack. As depicted from the figure, the *Meter Values* are stored intact in the blockchain architecture, hence ensuring the business continuity from the FDI attack for eMSPs that are offering the EV charging service. Furthermore, for the entire process, which lasted no longer than 12 minutes, 60,000 energy consumption measurements were generated, with each measurement to be intentionally considered as a single transaction.

The application's throughput and latency, are commonly measured in *Transactions Per Second* (TPS) and *Block Confirmation Time* (BCT) and offer essential performance evaluation criteria; since they define the number of transactions ordered, in each second, during the execution of the consensus protocol - and the elapsed time to confirm each transaction, respectively. The achieved performance metrics are presented in Fig. 8 in terms of TPS, total number of transactions and blocks stored in the distributed ledger, as well as latency measured in BCT. Particularly, Figures 8a and b illustrate that the blockchain application can order as high as 170 TPS and that all 60,000 *Meter Values* are processed during the application's evaluation during high load.

Meanwhile, Fig. 8c and d present the number of blocks generated by the ordering service and the time elapsed for each transaction to be confirmed by the validating peers, respectively. In each block, we have selected to store 10 transactions, leading to the creation of 6000 blocks, with each transaction requiring 2–8 ms to be confirmed. These perfor-

mance metrics are derived from monitoring and visualization tools as cAdvisor, Prometheus, Node-exporter and Grafana, which are built on-top of the proposed blockchain application⁷.

7. Conclusions

This article explores how blockchain technologies can be applied to enhance the detection and protection against cyber-threats that are targeting the EV-oriented infrastructure. These threats originate from the growing number of connectivity interfaces that the infrastructure includes. To achieve this goal, the article initially presents the EV infrastructure and ecosystem as well as the threat vectors that it includes, along with a threat taxonomy and the underlying TTPs for categorizing the threats according to standardized frameworks, such as the MITRE ATT&CK for Enterprise systems and the MITRE ICS ATT&CK. Then, the article continues by introducing a risk model for calculating the impact of cyber-attacks against the EV infrastructure and selecting the most prominent amongst them. Based on the identified threats, the application of blockchain technologies is examined for the main EV infrastructure services, including EV charging, energy trading and management.

Compared to the current literature, which commonly integrates blockchain technology for a single use case and adopts public-model designs, this article introduces a blockchain-enabled architecture to enhance the security of the EV infrastructure and incontrovertibly generalize the surveyed EV services. The proof-of-concept evaluation and the experimental results on an EV-oriented testbed illustrate the proposed framework's resilience against prominent attack scenarios in EV services, but also the exceptional performance metrics achieved, regarding throughput and latency, under a load testing approach.

As a part of future work, the proposed architecture will be transformed from a conceptually secure and sound framework into a real world and verifiably resilient platform suitable for large-scale deployments. Furthermore, we plan to expand on the EV-oriented services that were presented in this article, by incorporating, aside from EV charging, also energy trading and energy management. Additionally, the proposed architecture will be enhanced with succinct zero-knowledge proofs for preserving privacy and further reducing data linkage attacks; digital twins for stress-testing and validating scale readiness under realistic and new adversarial environments; as well as with crypto-agility and post quantum security for securing the attestation and the signing processes with disruption-free modernization.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Georgios Germanos: Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization; **Alexios Lekidis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization; **Sotirios Brotsis:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization; **Nicholas Kolokotronis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology.

⁷ <https://grafana.com/grafana/dashboards/10716-hyperledger-fabric/>

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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